

IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF SUPPLYING COTTON FARMS WITH MATERIAL AND TECHNICAL RESOURCES

Yuldasheva Shaxnoza

Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies
Teacher of the Department of Economics

Odiljonov Odiljon

He is a student of Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agro-Technology,
Department of Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13986184>

Abstract. The article analyzes the active measures implemented to provide the agrarian sector of our republic with modern local and foreign agricultural techniques in accordance with international standards and meeting the natural climate and soil conditions of the country's regions.

Key words: economic efficiency, profitability, key indicators, system, profit, material cost, income, cultivated area, gross product, productivity.

INTRODUCTION. Until now, farms have been operating mainly relying on restored agricultural machinery and using the services of MTPs. However, research shows that the quality and prices of services provided by MTPs do not always meet the demands of farmers.

In most cases, existing agricultural machinery and equipment have already passed their service life, both materially and morally. There is a shortage of means of supplying the existing equipment with components and providing technical services, the prices of components and agricultural machinery in general are very high, most of the farms are experiencing financial difficulties, material- limits the possibilities of updating the technical base.

Taking into account the above circumstances, the only correct way to strengthen the material and technical base of farms, to provide them with high-quality, modern equipment with a high level of labor is to make extensive use of leasing relations. The development of the leasing market is of great importance in providing agricultural machinery to newly established farms, when there is a lack of financial resources.

In the context of the development of market relations, attracting credit funds for agricultural development is a huge source of increasing the economic efficiency of production, in which the leasing system is a special form of loans for the renewal of fixed assets.

The experience of developed countries shows that the use of equipment leasing provides a solid basis for the formation and renewal of mobile fixed assets for farmers in a short period of time, as a result of which production efficiency increases. In particular, among the funds spent on agricultural machinery, the costs related to the leasing of machinery reach -30% in the USA, -8-10% in Austria, and -16% in England and France.

Also, more than 70 percent of the loans allocated by the bank for agriculture in England are allocated for the purchase of agricultural machinery, which indicates that the role of leasing relations in strengthening the material and technical base of the industry is incomparable.

If we pay more attention to the experience of foreign countries, the development of the issue of leasing of equipment was primarily caused by the fact that as a result of the development in the field of production of agricultural machinery, machine-building

enterprises fell into a strong competitive environment and it became difficult to sell their products. Equipment leasing is the best way to sell goods in the form of expensive equipment.

However, in the conditions of our republic, the development of the leasing market assumes the priority of somewhat different goals. That is, leasing is emerging as a means of eliminating the consequences of the farmer's solvency as a result of the differences in the formation of the prices of machinery and equipment and the prices of agricultural products in a situation where farmers' financial resources are insufficient. If we describe it differently, the leasing system solves the issue of renting agricultural machinery to users for a long period of time and provides for the payment of the cost of the leased machinery in equal amounts over a certain period of time. However, leasing is a much broader concept than renting or renting and has great advantages. These advantages are especially important for farmers who are just starting out. The use of equipment leasing allows farmers to simultaneously solve the following system of economic relations:

- solving the problem of the farmer's equipment rental:
- solving the issue of financing the process of using or acquiring equipment by a farmer:
- implementation of the process of exchange of equipment to the farmer

Figure 1. Problems to be solved in the delivery of equipment to farms on the basis of financial leasing

In other words, as a result of the use of leasing, farmers acquire the right not only to use this equipment, but also to own the equipment in a certain type of lease, in accordance with the amount of the lease payments, and to finance the purchase of equipment. they do. In addition, it will be possible to release financial resources and use private services for replenishment of working capital and other needs.

The most common types of agricultural equipment leasing are operational and financial leasing. In operational leasing - agricultural machinery is leased for shorter periods compared to the service life, in financial leasing - agricultural machinery is leased for a long period, during this period the full cost of agricultural machinery is paid to the seller, and after the end of the term then it becomes the property of the farmer. Therefore, financial leasing should be widely used to provide farms with equipment in our republic.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. A number of leading agrarian economists and theoreticians of our republic, including: A.A.Abdug'aniev, A.A.Shokirov, A.Joraev, A.Z.Zokirov, A.S.Samutali, D.Q.Ahmedov, N.S. Khushmatov, R.V. Abdullaev, R.Kh. Khusanov, F.Q.Qayumov, F.Kh.Nazarova, CH.M.Murodov, E.J.Yusupov, O'.P.Umurzakov, Q.A.Khasanjanov, Q.A.Choriev and others conducted scientific research.

RESULTS. Systematization of all the measures implemented in the cotton industry, their interdependence and proportional support should be aimed first of all at the production of raw cotton. The comprehensive support program for cotton raw material growers may include the following areas:

- ensuring profitable operation of cotton and other product growers by setting guaranteed purchase prices;
- providing grants and subsidies to producers of raw cotton and improving the financing and insurance system;
- to support the creation of promising varieties and the introduction of seed breeding systems and new technologies.

The internal and external cotton market in our republic varies depending on demand and supply, market conjuncture. In such conditions, it is necessary for the state to protect cotton growers from falling market prices. When the price on the market falls below the amount of the accepted costs or the base price, the difference must be paid by the state to the producers.

Although a part of the proceeds from the seeds sold to cotton-growing farms is directed to encourage breeders, it is not enough. Today, it is necessary to accelerate the direct support of the state for the scientific researches being carried out on the creation of a new variety.

The application of new technologies in cotton cultivation will ultimately bring high economic results. However, today, the economic situation of most cotton growers does not allow them to introduce new technologies that require a large amount of money, including mineral fertilizers along with drip and rain irrigation.

New technologies are of great importance in preserving the ecology of soil and water, as they give high results, and through the direct support of the state, the costs incurred by the state are covered directly and indirectly due to the increase in the amount of production and the saving of resources.

It is necessary to establish special loans for bringing technological equipment to cotton farms, and to give various incentives to banks that provide loans for the same purpose. For

this purpose, it would be appropriate to establish a special government fund. Financing the introduction of new technologies on a shared basis will also be beneficial for cotton growers.

Various factors affecting the economic efficiency of agrotechnical activities in the production of cotton raw materials and the problems that need to be solved have a negative impact on the effective operation of farms. This is an obstacle to awakening the interest of farmers in reducing costs and increasing the quality of products.

As a result, most of the farms engaged in cotton cultivation are forming as a relatively low-income industry. Therefore, the opportunities to invest in the development of cotton production and to ensure the material benefits of the workers employed in it are decreasing. Because the market demands from the cotton-producing farm to exceed the plan, to produce quality products, to make more income, and on this basis, to increase the income of the workers in the farm. At the same time, there are a number of factors that affect the timely and high-quality implementation of agrotechnical activities and do not allow to increase their efficiency.

The existence of situations such as non-effective use of available resources, excessive costs in product production have a negative impact on the efficiency of farm activities. For this purpose, it is appropriate to focus on activities that are of decisive importance in the implementation of the support process, that is, financial and economic activities.

In particular, the somewhat low purchase prices of raw cotton grown for state needs also limits the possibilities of purchasing new machinery for agricultural enterprises. If in 2000 it was necessary to sell 8.0 tons of cotton raw material to buy one MTZ-80 tractor, by 2016, 79.0 tons of cotton raw material should be sold to buy this tractor. is dying. That is, if the difference between agricultural and industrial goods is determined in kind, we can observe that the price of industrial goods has increased almost 10 times. This amount does not provide an opportunity to carry out high-quality agrotechnical activities and make payments. In order to prevent these problems, it is necessary to improve the loan allocation mechanism. In this:

- first, taking into account that the demand for this loan by farms will be relatively low due to the fact that the preferential loan is allocated only for cotton and grain crops, in the future, the preferential loan direction will be given to the farm growing all types of agricultural products. full implementation of the network;

- secondly, to create full opportunity, independence and freedom for farms to which credit is directed;

- thirdly, the system of allocating loans with a pledge of the future harvest to ensure the sustainable development of cotton farms, including the purchase of equipment, processing technologies, services and production of finished products should be focused on creating new jobs.

Advance money given to farmers who have a small amount of products sold for state needs through tranches does not give them the opportunity to make payments on time. As a result, either their creditor debts are increasing, or they cannot make payments for resources and services on time.

This does not give them the opportunity to grow products and carry out agrotechnical activities on time. In this:

- firstly, low effectiveness of advance funds;

- secondly, there is a disruption in agrotechnical activities in the production of agricultural products, which leads to a decrease in the volume of products;
- thirdly, the distribution of tranche money in this order has a negative effect on the work of farmers with a good financial condition.
- fourthly, the mechanism of providing short-term loans for the production of products not included in the state order in farms is also not functioning well.

A large price disparity can be observed between the price of agricultural products sold by farms and the price of agricultural machinery they buy from the industry.

In this case, state support to farms should serve to reduce the price disparity and develop farms. To eliminate these problems in the field of cotton production, first of all, it is necessary to develop the following organizational and economic measures to increase the efficiency of agrotechnical activities:

- provision of material and technical resources at the required level in the implementation of agrotechnical activities, autumn plowing of cultivated fields, preparation of land for planting, sowing of seeds, processing between cotton rows, defoliation and cotton harvesting in a timely manner increases;

- in the implementation of agrotechnical measures, to determine the promising cotton varieties, optimal tillage, the ratio of necessary organic and mineral fertilizers, timely completion of irrigation works according to the established norms, from cotton fields increases productivity and provides cost savings;

- use of efficient methods of economic management by developing and retraining the skills of specialists and workers responsible for agrotechnical activities, developing a mechanism for their economic stimulation creates opportunities to provide.

According to our researches and the experiences of foreign countries, it is necessary to carry out coordinated and encouraging support measures of the state in the implementation of agrotechnical activities in cotton growing in a targeted and targeted manner. That is, as it was justified in the previous stages of our research, in practice, innovative activity is carried out through direct and indirect incentive mechanisms.

Therefore, they also apply innovative products or developments in their production activities, for example, various innovative drugs or bio-fertilizers, drip irrigation of crops, increasing soil fertility, and new technologies in similar areas. In such cases, it is appropriate to establish appropriate benefits for these types of taxes.

- Although the participants in the cotton production system in Uzbekistan, especially the producers, are supported to a certain extent by the state, in this direction, it is necessary to adopt a state program that covers all issues in a comprehensive manner, to integrate all the agrotechnical activities being carried out into one system, to It is desirable to work on implementation in a proportionate manner. In today's conditions, such support should be aimed primarily at cotton producers. The support program for cotton producers should include the following directions:

- providing grants and subsidies to cotton growers;
- to ensure profitable operation of producers by setting guaranteed purchase prices;
- improvement of the financing system of cotton production;
- creating new varieties and supporting the seed breeding system;
- supporting the introduction of new technologies;

- support of the insurance system for compensation of damages caused by natural disasters, etc.

CONCLUSION. According to research, the following should be implemented in order to develop the leasing system for providing farms with agricultural machinery:

- the legal basis for providing agricultural enterprises with equipment on the basis of leasing should be improved;
- formation of a competitive environment through extensive development of the private sector in the field of leasing companies engaged in the leasing of agricultural machinery;
- training of qualified specialists engaged in the leasing of agricultural machinery, sending them to study and improve their qualifications in foreign countries, or organizing training courses with the participation of foreign specialists;
- tax policy on the activities of leasing companies, introduction of an effective economic system that guarantees the return of financing companies and bank funds;
- it is necessary to introduce the legal-normative basis and economic mechanisms of financing leasing operations directly through the bank.

Increasing the efficiency of cotton cultivation in farms includes the following directions:

- Increases gross yield by 2% due to increased attention to seed materials;
- As a result of improving agrotechnical measures in cotton cultivation, it is possible to increase the gross yield by 5-10%. For example, the widespread introduction of drip irrigation system creates an opportunity to increase the efficiency of agricultural production. In this case, material costs can be reduced up to two times. The use of US and Chinese agrotechnologies in cotton farming has been proven to reduce costs by 7-10%;
- It will be possible to increase the gross yield by 2% due to increased attention to the harvesting of the grown crops.

The support program for cotton producers should include the following directions:

- providing grants and subsidies to cotton growers;
- to ensure profitable operation of producers by setting guaranteed purchase prices;
- improvement of the financing system of cotton production;
- creating new varieties and supporting the seed breeding system;
- supporting the introduction of new technologies;
- support of the insurance system for compensation of damages caused by natural disasters, etc.

References:

1. Shermatov O.A. Iqtisodiyotni erkinlashtirish sharoitida paxtachilikni rivojlantirish va uning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari. Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan avtoreferat. — T.: O'zBIITI, 2006. 27 b.;
2. Murtazoev O. Paxta kompleksi samaradorligining metodik masalalari. Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan avtoreferat. T.: O'zBIITI, 2009. - B.12.
3. Murtazoev O. Paxta kompleksi samaradorligining metodik masalalari. Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan avtoreferat. T.: O'zBIITI, 2009. - B.12.
4. Yuldasheva Shaxnoza, Olimjonova Farogat. (2023). AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT POTENTIAL. INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN SCIENCE, 2(3), 66–70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7778308>

5. Yuldasheva Shahnoza, Faxriddinova Dilobar. (2023). ORGANIZING NEW TOURISM DESTINATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(2), 182–184. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7683651>
6. Yuldasheva Shahnoza, Faxriddinova Dilobar. (2023). THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES OF DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY OF COTTON RAW PRODUCTION. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(2), 58–61. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7620997>
7. Yuldasheva Shaxnoza, Ismatova Nigora. (2023). IMPROVING THE STATE SUPPORT SYSTEM OF THE COTTON NETWORK. SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY, 2(2), 187–191. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7676504>
8. Yuldasheva Shahnoza, Faxriddinova Dilobar. (2023). ORGANIZING NEW TOURISM DESTINATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(2), 182–184. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7683651>
9. Yuldasheva Shahnoza, Faxriddinova Dilobar. (2023). THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES OF DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY OF COTTON RAW PRODUCTION. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(2), 58–61. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7620997>
10. Yuldasheva Shaxnoza, Ismatova Nigora. (2023). IMPROVING THE STATE SUPPORT SYSTEM OF THE COTTON NETWORK. SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY, 2(2), 187–191. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7676504>

